

A) Comparisons with hippocampal translomic studies



B) Comparisons of excitatory translome with hippocampal translomic studies



C) Comparisons of excitatory translome with hippocampal translomic studies



D) Comparisons of *Pvalb* interneuronal translome with hippocampal translomic studies



E) Comparisons of *Pvalb* interneuronal translome with hippocampal translomic studies

